

Psychology in Action: Integrating Psychological Science, Policy and Practice to Solve Societal problems

Report of the 2025 Annual Scientific Conference of the Nigerian Psychological Association (NPA) at Faculty of Social Sciences Auditorium, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

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1.0 PREAMBLE

The Nigerian Psychological Association (NPA) held its 2025 Annual Scientific Conference from 26th to 30th August 2025 at Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The conference which was organised by the Ebonyi State Chapter of NPA brought together psychologists, scholars, administrators and stakeholders on mental health from across the country to deliberate on key issues affecting psychology and its application to the Nigerian society. The conference also provided a platform to highlight the contributions of psychology to addressing contemporary social, political, and economic challenges, while emphasizing the importance of strengthening the profession in Nigeria.

2.0 OBJECTIVES

The conference aimed to:

- Highlight the role of psychology in addressing Nigeria's pressing societal challenges, including insecurity, drug abuse, and mental health concerns.
- Review the status of psychology education and practice in Nigeria, with a focus on curriculum reform and licensure.
- Promote collaboration between psychology professionals, government, and stakeholders for national development.
- Celebrate distinguished scholars and induct new members into the College of Chartered Psychologists.

3.0 PARTICIPANTS

The conference was attended by psychologists, academics, students, government representatives, and members of professional bodies including the Pan African Psychology Union (PAPU). Delegates came from universities across Nigeria and from partner institutions abroad.

4.0 OPENING

Prof. Michael Ezenwa, the Chairman of the ceremony, welcomed participants by highlighting the importance of psychology in addressing contemporary societal challenges such as drug abuse, inflation, and suicide. He emphasized the need for establishing psychological service centres in universities for both students and staff, drawing attention to the urgent demand for mental health services across Nigeria.

Prof Ezenwa, a former President of the NPA, also reflected on the bill on psychology that was not signed into law by the previous administration at the national level in Nigeria and expressed hope that renewed efforts would push it through in the current political dispensation. He concluded by warmly welcoming everyone to the conference and setting a tone of optimism and collaboration for the days ahead.

4.1 GOODWILL MESSAGES

Prof. Nkechi Emma Echiegu, Dean of Faculty of Social Sciences, emphasized the theme of the conference and the achievements of the faculty in advancing psychology services, welcoming everyone to the institution and the state.

Prof. Ogbu Chigozie, the immediate past Vice chancellor of the University represented by Prof. Ngozi Emeka Nwobia (former dean of Faculty of Social Sciences at EBSU) expressed warm words of welcome to participants.

Prof. Michael Awoke, represented by Prof. Michael Aja-Nwachukwu, praised psychology as ‘the master’ discipline and expressed his admiration for its relevance to national development.

5.0 ADDRESS BY NPA PRESIDENT

The NPA President, **Prof Olukayode Afolabi**, began by acknowledging that this would be his last conference as President. He appreciated the contributions of colleagues, stakeholders, and members who supported his administration throughout his tenure.

Prof Afolabi addressed pressing challenges facing Nigeria, particularly insecurity, and emphasized the role of psychological principles in tackling such issues. He also called for reforms in

psychology curricula to align with modern societal needs and urged the incoming administration to sustain and improve on the legacies already built.

6.0 SPEECH BY PRESIDENT OF PAPU

Prof. Andrew Zamani, President of the Pan African Psychology Union (PAPU), reflected on the Union's vision of uniting psychological practices across Africa. He announced the inauguration of the Student Forum of the Union and emphasized the significance of expanding membership to include both organizational and student categories.

He highlighted achievements made under his leadership, especially the development of a continental framework to address mental health challenges, stressing that African psychology should both integrate international practices and preserve indigenous knowledge.

7.0 KEYNOTE ADDRESS

Dr. Thomas Attah, in his keynote speech, emphasized the urgent need to bridge the gap between psychological research and real-world applications, translating knowledge into actionable policies.

He critiqued religious institutions for their inability to fully address societal issues and stressed the importance of parenting interventions, such as workshops and counseling, to mitigate behavioural problems among youth. He discussed marital breakdowns and the collapse of family structures, noting the importance of premarital counseling and relationship education as preventive strategies.

Dr Attah further explored challenges of depression, loneliness, and irresponsible behaviour in the digital age, particularly the psychological consequences of uncontrolled social media usage and reckless driving habits.

The speaker concluded by urging psychologists to collaborate with communities and stakeholders to design practical interventions and policies, ensuring psychology remains relevant and impactful in solving real-world problems.

8.0 LEAD PAPER PRESENTATION 1

The Anambra State Commissioner for Information, **Dr. Law Mefor**, represented by Dr. Ada Dike, delivered a paper on the role of education and technology in national development. He emphasized psychology as the foundation for progress in governance and societal growth, using Anambra State as a model of innovation.

He spoke extensively on the role of good governance in promoting human capital development, describing education as the true bedrock of progress in any nation. He highlighted the need for technological innovation as a driver of youth empowerment, stressing that technology and psychology can work hand in hand to address unemployment and enhance national productivity.

Leadership, according to him, is the major driver of innovation, and he urged Nigeria to invest in transformative leadership that empowers young people and builds sustainable systems for development. The commissioner who is a forensic and social psychologist concluded by calling for psychology to be more central in national planning and education policy, ensuring that human capital development is grounded in sound psychological principles.

8.1 LEAD PAPER PRESENTATION 2

Dr. Remi Opeyemi spoke on bridging the borders of psychology through comparative insights. He began by critiquing the theoretical nature of Nigeria's psychology curriculum and emphasized the urgent need to incorporate practical training for students.

He shared personal experiences as a licensed psychologist in Canada, highlighting the difference in exposure and practice between Nigeria and developed nations. He underscored that practical application is vital to solving Nigeria's mental health problems.

According to Dr Opeyemi, key challenges identified included lack of a unified national licensure system, weak enforcement of professional standards by the NPA, and low recognition of psychology in Nigeria's public sectors. He also pointed to the persistent stigma attached to mental health issues.

He recommended solutions such as standardizing the psychology curriculum across institutions, integrating psychology into schools and the justice system, and expanding postgraduate specialization options. He stressed the importance of ethics and professional discipline in practice.

Key strategies he proposed included introducing a national licensure examination, culturally adapting psychological interventions to Nigerian contexts, and ensuring full integration of psychology into the public sector to maximize its impact.

8.2 LEAD PAPER PRESENTATION 3

Prof. Pawel Boski, a precursor of cross-cultural psychology in Poland, began by reflecting on his historical experiences teaching and researching psychology across Nigerian universities. He recounted his engagements with students and faculty, noting the challenges and opportunities psychology faces in Nigeria.

His paper examined economic antecedents of cultural dimensions, situating Nigeria within global maps of psychological research and comparing Nigeria with other developing nations.

Prof Boski discussed psychological consequences of cultural systems, showing how values and traditions shape behaviour, motivation, and social interaction in Nigeria's socio-economic context.

He analyzed contemporary empirical problems in research using Marxist, Weberian, and McClelland models, emphasizing their relevance to Nigeria's cultural and economic realities.

The renowned scholar and author of the book "*Cultural Psychology and Acculturation*," concluded by urging Nigerian psychologists to engage more in cross-cultural studies and to position Nigerian psychology on the global research map while strengthening indigenous perspectives.

8.3 ABSTRACT PRESENTATIONS

Over 200 abstracts were presented during plenary sessions by the conference participants.

9.0 HONORARY AWARDS AND FELLOWS

Honorary Awards were conferred on:

- Prof. Michael Awoke (VC, Ebonyi State University)
- Prof. Chigozie Ogbu (Past Vice Chancellor, EBSU)
- Prof. Paul Olisaemeka Ezeonu (Provost of the College of Medicine, Alex Ekwueme Federal University Teaching Hospital, Abakalki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria).
- Dr. Mohammed Aminuzami (HOD, Economics Department, University of Ilorin)

Newly Inducted Chartered Psychologists:

- Prof. Olukayode Afolabi
- Prof. Andrew Zamani
- Prof. Michael Ezenwa
- Prof. Harry Obi-Nwosu
- Prof. Shyngle Balogun
- Rev. Sr. Theresa Chinyere Eke
- Prof. Lanre Adebayo
- Prof. Sunday Idemudia
- Prof. Adegbenga Sunmola
- Prof. Nyitor Shenge
- Prof. Grace Adejuwon
- Prof. David Okurame
- Prof. Temitayo Adewuyi
- Prof. Barnabas Nwankwo
- Prof. Ogwo Ogechi
- Prof. Ronke Awopetu
- Prof. Iyabode Akinbobola
- Prof. Emenike Anyaegbulam
- Prof. Julie Enewa Orshi
- Rev. Fr. Dr. Okoli Paul Chibuike

- Dr. Afolabi Aroyewun
- Dr. Perpetua Ngosoo
- Dr. Alex Igundunasse
- Dr. Chioma Igboegwu
- Dr. Abubakar Tafida
- Dr. Oluyemi Atibioke
- Dr. Irene Ofili
- Dr. Judith Ayangeawam
- Dr. Anyalewa Ajonye
- Dr. Ada Maduka
- Dr. Bolayoko Ibiyemi
- Dr. Akanidomo Ibanga
- Dr. Casmir Nwankwo
- Dr. Uche Aondoaver
- Dr. Adaobi Eze
- Dr. Ronald Charles Oginyi
- Dr. Sampson Kelechi Nwonyi
- Dr. Izuchukwu Ndukaihe
- Dr. Remi Opayemi
- Dr. Samson Kolawole
- Dr. Samuel Success Haruna
- Dr. James Abel
- Dr. Hauwa Agboje
- Dr. Joshua Gandi

10.0 VOTE OF THANKS

Dr. Sampson Kelechi Nwonyi, Chairman of the Local Organizing Committee, delivered the vote of thanks in a detailed appreciation. He acknowledged the NPA for granting them the hosting rights, expressed gratitude to the NPA President and members for their support, and commended the organizing committee for their dedication and teamwork. He concluded by thanking all participants for making the conference a resounding success.